

The 2024-2025 elections in Romania: From local elections to the international impact of political choices (II)

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This special issue on the 2024 and 2025 (unexpected) elections in Romania aims to help in understanding better the impact of these elections, from the local level to international political implications. The special issue is published in two parts, as issues 1 and 2 of volume 25 of the *Romanian Journal of Political Science*. The first part, published in June 2025, included six articles that approached the elections primarily from political science perspectives.

The first article (Ștefanachi and Grecu, 2025) analyzed the Romanian parliamentary elections using the economic voting framework, focusing on the links between economic factors, party preferences, and incumbent party reelection, concluding that economic factors alone are insufficient in explaining voting. The second article (Angi, Bădescu, and Radu, 2025) analyzed the factors affecting voters' preferences in the 2025 presidential elections in Romania, combining economic and cultural explanations for electoral support for populism. The central contribution of this article consists of using Covid-19 vaccination rates as a contextual indicator of deeper cultural and epistemic orientations related to trust in expertise, state authority, religiosity, and moral traditionalism.

The next two articles both approached the elections placing their focus on the appearance of the mysterious Călin Georgescu candidate that managed to derail the 2024 presidential elections. Starting from the criminal charges brought against Georgescu, Bucur (2025) developed a tool for measuring in a systematic way contemporary fascist discourse in Romania, analyzing the doctrinal convergence between classical European fascism and the public discourse promoted by Călin Georgescu. He concluded that contemporary radical discourses can and should be analyzed using standardized measurement tools that are historically comparable and legally relevant. Copilaș (2025) analyzed Eurasianism, arguing that its newest branch has developed in Romania, as exemplified by the writings and public statements of Călin Georgescu.

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The last two articles in the first part of the special issue focused on young voters. Tavalla and Matiuța (2025) investigated the role of the TikTok platform in shaping nationalist populism and affective polarization among young Romanians during the 2024-2025 Romanian presidential elections and showed how TikTok functions as an incubator for affective nationalism by amplifying far-right narratives and mobilizing young people through emotional media content. Petrila and Turcescu (2025) analyzed the mechanisms that shape the electoral participation of first-time voters through a comparative analysis between Romania and Austria and showed that youth turnout is influenced by a broader civic ecosystem that includes family socialization, civic education, institutional support, and the digital environment.

This, second, part of the special issue brings together a series of five articles that analyze the elections from perspectives that belong to international relations and foreign affairs and is closed by two papers that analyze specific aspects of the elections from a political science or a sociological perspective.

The opening article, by Mișcoiu and Naumescu (2025) explores public reactions and how the presidential elections in Romania, both those canceled in November 2024 and those repeated in May 2025, were perceived in Western democracies and by the authoritarian revisionist regime in the Russian Federation. One of the most heated and critical moments in the post-1989 Romanian democracy produced significant reactions in the US, France, Germany, the United Kingdom, and Italy, as well as in Moscow, reflecting on a small scale the tense context in Europe and in the system of international relations, as well as the competitive ideological orientation of the main capitals in this context of change.

Starting from the statements, official documents, press releases, and messages issued by political leaders and authorities in the major powers mentioned above regarding the elections in Romania, Mișcoiu and Naumescu argued that the external impact and the reporting of global actors on the recent presidential elections in Romania reflected, in fact, the hybrid war and major turmoil in international politics, Russia's revisionist attempts, and the redefinition of relations between the major powers. Given Romania's position, at a geopolitical periphery, on the edge of NATO and the EU, a failure and collapse of democracy, liberal values, and the pro-Western direction would have sent a strong message to the region and Europe.

Ciot and Vănoagă (2025) provide a comparative analysis of sovereigntist political responses to climate policy by examining how climate agendas are framed in the 2024 presidential campaigns in Romania and the United States. Through qualitative document analysis of electoral programs, the two authors show that climate policy has moved beyond a primarily technocratic domain to become a central arena of conflict for political identity construction and electoral mobilization. Despite the differing institutional and national contexts, sovereigntist candidates converge in reframing climate policy around themes of sovereignty, energy security, and cost of living rather than decarbonization targets. By comparing the positions of the Romanian candidates to Trump's electoral platform, the article identifies transnational patterns in sovereigntist discourse, highlighting how climate policies are selectively appropriated, contested, or reinterpreted to support broader nationalist political agendas. In addition to the comparison of the two cases, the paper also extends the literature on populism and the green transition to Central and Eastern Europe, indicating how electoral politics reshapes the meaning and political function of climate governance across different democratic contexts.

Balaș and Pantea (2025) examine the electoral behavior of Romanian citizens abroad in the 2025 presidential elections and challenge the widespread assumption that the diaspora constitutes a politically homogeneous electorate. Using electoral data at the precinct level, the authors demonstrate

that voting patterns in the diaspora are structured by geographic and socio-political cleavages, most notably between voters residing in EU/Schengen+UK countries and those living elsewhere. The study shows that support for competing presidential candidates varied systematically across these contexts and even within host countries, revealing significant internal fragmentation shaped by migration experiences, levels of integration, and local socio-economic environments. By disaggregating diaspora voting outcomes and reconstructing its territorial and social heterogeneity, the article reconceptualizes the Romanian diaspora as multiple diasporas with distinct political preferences and motivations. The paper also discusses how transnational migration contexts reshape electoral behavior and complicate conventional expectations about emigrant voters' ideological orientations in contemporary democracies.

If the previous article focused on the Romanian diaspora in the EU, Brie and Putină (2025) analyze the voting behavior in the 2025 Romanian presidential elections among Romanian citizens residing in the Republic of Moldova, situating electoral behavior within a broader framework of transnational politics, identity dynamics, and regional geopolitics. Moving beyond a purely electoral analysis, the study combines turnout data, voting results, and an examination of public discourse to show how participation and vote choice were shaped simultaneously by domestic Romanian politics, Moldovan internal debates, and the wider geopolitical environment marked by the war in Ukraine and competing European and Russian influences. Brie and Putină show that the high levels of voter mobilization in the Republic of Moldova reflect not only electoral preferences but also identity affiliation, perceptions of Romania as a strategic partner, and expectations regarding Moldova's European trajectory. By conceptualizing voting as a transnational political act embedded in identity construction and geopolitical positioning, the article shows how elections in a country of origin can function as instruments of symbolic alignment and political signaling in neighboring states with overlapping citizenship and contested geopolitical orientations.

The article by Corpădean (2025) examines how the Republic of Moldova became a central thematic reference point in the Romanian presidential elections of 2024–2025, demonstrating how foreign policy issues can be internalized and politicized within domestic electoral competition. Through a discourse analysis of campaign programs, speeches, and party positioning, Corpădean shows that the Republic of Moldova functioned less as a conventional foreign policy topic and more as a symbolic political resource through which candidates articulated competing visions of national identity, regional strategy, and Romania's place within the European and Euro-Atlantic order. The analysis reveals a clear ideological cleavage: pro-European candidates framed Moldova primarily as a strategic partner in EU integration and regional stability, whereas nationalist and populist actors instrumentalized the issue through reunification narratives and identity-based mobilization. By bridging electoral studies with foreign policy analysis, the article's contribution lies in demonstrating how external relations, especially with a historically and culturally connected neighboring state, can structure domestic political polarization and serve as a lens through which broader tensions between liberal internationalism and sovereigntist politics become visible in contemporary Romanian democracy.

Brihan and Petrilă (2025) investigate how EU-related themes are included and approached into the electoral platforms of Romanian political parties during the 2024 European Parliament and parliamentary elections, focusing on the interaction between national political competition and EU multilevel governance. Through a qualitative comparative analysis of the programs of the seven parties that passed the electoral thresholds in the two types of elections, the authors demonstrate that references to European policies, values, and obligations vary systematically according to party ideology and political positioning, revealing clear differences between pro-European and populist actors. Pro-

European parties tend to interpret EU membership as a framework for modernization, policy coordination, and strategic development, while populist parties selectively reinterpret European issues through sovereignty-centered or critical narratives. By linking party discourse to the priorities of European political groups and to the institutional logic of EU governance, the article's contribution lies in indicating how Europeanization operates not only as a policy process but also as an electoral framing mechanism that structures political competition and democratic debate in Romania. More broadly, the paper advances understanding of how national parties translate EU-level agendas into domestic political language, highlighting the role of electoral programs as mediators between European integration and national democratic contestation.

The next two papers in this special issue move away from international relations perspectives and bring the focus back on political science and sociology. Iov (2025) investigates how Romanian students perceive the relationship between nationalist parties and the sustainability of democracy in the context of the 2024 European Parliament elections, offering an empirically grounded perspective on the political attitudes of a younger generation often underexamined in studies of populism and democratic resilience. Based on survey data collected from 417 students, the study demonstrates that attitudes toward nationalist parties are structured by socio-demographic factors (especially education, age, gender, and socio-economic status), and that higher educational attainment is associated with more critical evaluations of nationalist actors and greater concern about their potential impact on democratic institutions. Rather than treating nationalism solely as a party-system phenomenon, the article shifts analytical attention to perception formation, showing how trust, political information, and civic awareness shape young citizens' assessments of democratic risks such as misinformation, polarization, and institutional erosion. The paper's main contribution lies in linking debates on democratic backsliding and nationalism to political socialization processes among youth, thereby highlighting how generational attitudes may influence the future trajectory of democratic legitimacy and European integration in Romania.

Chirodea, Marian, and Bekesi (2025) take advantage of the fact that regional inequalities remain a defining feature of Romania's development, with persistent gaps between dynamic urban growth poles and peripheral rural or small-town areas. These disparities influence not only economic opportunities but also political perceptions of fairness, representation, and government performance. As a result, electoral behavior in Romania is strongly territorially embedded, reflecting voters' experiences of development and marginalization rather than only ideological alignment. It is within this context they examine the relationship between regional development dynamics and electoral behavior by analyzing how socio-economic conditions shape voting patterns in the four counties that compose the North-West Development Region in Romania during the second round of the 2025 presidential elections. Combining electoral geography with quantitative analysis of official electoral and socio-economic indicators, Chirodea, Marian, and Bekesi show that electoral preferences are closely associated with territorial development patterns, urban–rural structures, and educational characteristics rather than with income levels alone. Voters' choices reflect locally embedded perceptions of development, governance performance, and community well-being, with distinct voting behaviors emerging across different types of urban centers and rural areas. The article's contribution lies in linking micro-regional development disparities to electoral outcomes, illustrating how uneven territorial development functions as a structural driver of political preferences and how local socio-economic contexts mediate support for progressive versus sovereigntist political options in contemporary Romanian elections.

The special issue is closed by an article that stands apart from all the others. Preda and Preda (2025) offer a social-theological and epistemological interpretation of recent Romanian electoral dynamics, arguing that contemporary political crises cannot be fully understood through institutional or strategic explanations alone but must be situated within a deeper anthropological transformation affecting citizens' capacity for judgment. Drawing on political theology, philosophy, and post-totalitarian studies, Preda and Preda conceptualize electoral behavior as increasingly shaped by affective recognition, charismatic authority, and cognitive fatigue rather than deliberative reasoning. They advance the argument that in post-totalitarian societies freedom risks becoming merely procedural when discernment is delegated to leaders, when digital environments privilege emotional confirmation over verification, and when political discourse appropriates religious symbolism to sacralize authority. The article's principal contribution lies in reframing democratic vulnerability as an epistemic and anthropological problem, one rooted in the erosion of discernment and the weakening of the subject capable of sustaining democratic freedom, thereby extending debates on populism and democratic backsliding beyond institutional analysis toward questions of knowledge, truth, and political anthropology. Although placed in a different paradigm, we do believe Preda and Preda's arguments do address many of the issues discussed in the other papers in this double special issue and they can be used to reframe some of the discussions we have had and, most likely, will continue to have with respect to the fate of the Romanian democracy in the near future.

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